

SMARANDACHE FRIENDLY NUMBERS AND A FEW MORE SEQUENCES

(Amarnath Murthy, S.E.(E&T) , WLS, Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd., Sabarmati,
Ahmedabad,- 380005 INDIA.)

If the sum of any set of consecutive terms of a sequence = the product of the first and the last number of the set then this pair is called a **Smarndache Friendly Pair** with respect to the sequence.

{1} SMARANDACHE FRIENDLY NATURAL NUMBER PAIRS:

e.g. Consider the natural number sequence

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, ...

then the Smarandache friendly pairs are

(1,1), (3, 6) , (15,35) , (85, 204), ... etc.

as $3 + 4 + 5 + 6 = 18 = 3 \times 6$

$15 + 16 + 17 + \dots + 33 + 34 + 35 = 525 = 15 \times 35$ etc.

There exist infinitely many such pairs. This is evident from the fact that if (m, n) is a friendly pair then so is the pair (2n+m, 5n +2m -1). Ref [1].

{2} SMARANDACHE FRIENDLY PRIME PAIRS:

Consider the prime number sequence

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 23, 29, ...

we have $2 + 3 + 5 = 10 = 2 \times 5$, Hence (2, 5) is a friendly prime pair.

$3 + 5 + 7 + 11 + 13 = 39 = 3 \times 13$, (3,13) is a friendly prime pair.

$5 + 7 + 11 + \dots + 23 + 29 + 31 = 155 = 5 \times 31$, (5, 31) is a friendly prime pair.

Similarly (7, 53) is also a Smarandache friendly prime pair. In a friendly prime pair (p, q) we define q as the big brother of p.

Open Problems: (1) Are there infinitely many friendly prime pairs?

2. Are there big brothers for every prime?

{3} SMARANDACHE UNDER-FRIENDLY PAIR:

If the sum of any set of consecutive terms of a sequence is a **divisor** of the product of the first and the last number of the set then this pair is called a **Smarndache under- Friendly Pair** with respect to the sequence.

{4} SMARANDACHE OVER-FRIENDLY PAIR:

If the sum of any set of consecutive terms of a sequence is a **multiple** of the product of the first and the last number of the set then this pair is called a **Smarndache Over- Friendly Pair** with respect to the sequence.

{5} SMARANDACHE SIGMA DIVISOR PRIME SEQUENCE:

The sequence of primes p_n , which satisfy the following congruence.

$n-1$

$$\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} p_r \equiv 0 \pmod{p_n}$$

$r=1$

2, 5, 71, ...

5 divides 10, and 71 divides $568 = 2 + 3 + 5 + \dots + 67$

Problems: (1) Is the above sequence infinite?

Conjecture: Every prime divides at least one such cumulative sum.

{6} SMARANDACHE SMALLEST NUMBER WITH 'n' DIVISORS SEQUENCE:

1, 2, 4, 6, 16, 12, 64, 24, 36, 48, 1024, ...

$d(1) = 1, d(2) = 2, d(4) = 3, d(6) = 4, d(16) = 5, d(12) = 6$ etc. , $d(T_n) = n$, where T_n is **smallest such number.**

It is evident $T_p = 2^{p-1}$, if p is a prime.

The sequence T_n+1 is

2, 3, 5, 7, 17, 13, 65, 25, 37, 49, 1025, ...

Conjectures: (1) The above sequence contains infinitely many primes.

(2) The only Mersenne's prime it contains is 7.

(3) The above sequence contains infinitely many perfect squares.

{7} SMARANDACHE INTEGER PART k^n SEQUENCE (SIPS) :

****In this sequence k is a non integer. For example:**

(i) SMARANDACHE INTEGER PART π^n SEQUENCE:

$[\pi^1], [\pi^2], [\pi^3], [\pi^4], \dots$

3, 9, 31, 97, ...

(ii) SMARANDACHE INTEGER PART e^n SEQUENCE:

$[e^1], [e^2], [e^3], [e^4], \dots$

2, 7, 20, 54, 148, 403, ...

Conjecture: Every SIPS contains infinitely many primes.

{8} Smarandache Summable Divisor Pairs (SSDP):

Pair of numbers (m, n) which satisfy the following relation

$$d(m) + d(n) = d(m + n)$$

e.g. we have $d(2) + d(10) = d(12)$, $d(3) + d(5) = d(8)$, $d(4) + d(256) = d(260)$,

$d(8) + d(22) = d(30)$, etc.

hence $(2, 10)$, $(3, 5)$, $(4, 256)$, $(8, 22)$ are SSPDs.

Conjecture: (1) There are infinitely many SSDPs?

(2) For every integer m there exists a number n such that (m, n) is an SSDP.

{9} SMARANDACHE REIMANN ZETA SEQUENCE

6, 90, 945, 93555, 638512875, ...

where T_n is given by the following relation of

$$z(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \pi^{2n} / T_n$$

Conjecture: No two terms of this sequence are relatively prime.

Consider the sequence obtained by incrementing each term by one

7, 91, 946, 9451, 93556, 638512876, ...

Problem: How many primes does the above sequence contain?

{10} SMARANDACHE PRODUCT OF DIGITS SEQUENCE:

The n^{th} term of this sequence is defined as $T_n =$ product of the digits of n .

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, ...

{11} SMARANDACHE SIGMA PRODUCT OF DIGITS NATURAL SEQUENCE:

The n^{th} term of this sequence is defined as the sum of the products of all the numbers from 1 to n .

1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, 28, 36, 45, 45, 46, 48, 51, 55, 60, 66, 73, 81, 90, 90, 92, 96, ...

Here we consider the terms of the sequence for some values of n .

For $n = 9$ we have $T_n = 45$, The sum of all the single digit numbers = 45

For $n = 99$ we have $T_n = 2070 = 45^2 + 45..$

Similarly we have $T_{999} = (T_9)^3 + (T_9)^2 + T_9 = 45^3 + 45^2 + 45 = (45^4 - 1) / (45 - 1) = (45^4 - 1) / 44$

The above proposition can easily be proved.

This can be further generalized for a number system with base 'b' ($b = 10$, the decimal system has already been considered.)

For a number system with base 'b' the $(b^r - 1)^{\text{th}}$ term in the Smarandache sigma product of digits sequence is

$$2\{ \{ b(b-1)/2 \}^{r+1} - 1 \} / \{ b^2 - b - 2 \}$$

Further Scope: The task ahead is to find the n^{th} term in the above sequence for an arbitrary value of n .

{12} SMARANDACHE SIGMA PRODUCT OF DIGITS ODD SEQUENCE:

1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 26, 29, 34, 41, 50, 52, 58, 68, 82, 100, 103, 112, 127, 148, ...

It can be proved that for $n = 10^r - 1$, T_n is the sum of the r terms of the Geometric progression with the first term as 25 and the common ratio as 45.

{13} SMARANDACHE SIGMA PRODUCT OF DIGITS EVEN SEQUENCE:

2, 6, 12, 20, 20, 22, 26, 32, 40, 40, 44, 52, 62, 78, 78, 84, 96, 114, 138, ...

It can again be proved that for $n = 10^r - 1$, T_n is the sum of the r terms of the Geometric progression with the first term as 20 and the common ratio as 45.

Open Problem: Are there infinitely many common members in {12} and {13} ?

Reference:

[1] Problem2/31, M&IQ ,3/99 Volume 9, Sept' 99, Bulgaria.